

The concept of honesty in English and Uzbek languages

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ANNOTATION

This is it article English and Uzbek of the concept of "Honesty" in their languages semantic to the analysis is dedicated. Also this "Honesty" concept in the article English and Uzbek in linguistic culture similarity and different aspects are also open is given Honesty of the lexeme main, important features moral narrow group interests, ideological or practical from thoughts, corporate superior to put honesty lexeme of norms objective content reflection bringer universal call it nature need

Key words: concept, honesty, culture, national culture, linguistic and cultural , socio-cultural reality , value

INTRODUCTION

Cognitive linguistics - language and mind between relationships problems , the world conceptualization and in categorization of the tongue role , cognitive in processes and a person experience In general , the individual cognitive of a person abilities with dependence and language and their mutually effect forms learning linguistics direction. Concept cognitive of a linguist support concept is considered He is in linguistics concept , thought , idea , understanding and that's it similar comments with is conducted . The word concept comes from the Latin conceptus, which means " understanding " . represents _ A lot In some cases, the word " concept " is derived from the term " concept " . synonym as when used , " Concept " is the subject or the event main symbol represents , and " Concept " is about him common and wider information in itself embodies .

Eat. of S. Kubryakova to his opinion according to , the term " concept " means thinking , understanding , information storage and again work such as problems with engaged in cognitive psychology and cognitive Linguistics , Linguistic Culture sciences for " umbrella " function it will come . (1,2)

To all of us known near from years since concept to the word of linguistics separately learning object as attention is being directed.

Concept modern in linguistics linguistic and cultural of the field unit is considered because it is language, society and his culture about knowledge embodies. This concept in the language culture reflection makes and a person in his mind universe image forms.

" Concept of thinking operative content unit, systematized of knowledge unit or is a quantum" .(3) " Concepts are a person thinking in the process uses an ideal, abstract units are meanings . They are received knowledge experience, the real existence of a person perception reach of the results content certain units , in the form of " quanta ". reflection " (4). Various concepts of the lexicon semantic interpretation , certain units to the complex relatedness with is characterized .

"NN Boldirev's stated , " in the language concept separately words and word combinations , phraseological units , sentences and whole texts by means of verbalized to be possible "(5).

We know that every one of the area active applied many there are concepts. Including them oral and written in speech existence with from others separate stands _ This in the article to the above relied on without " Honesty " concept deeper definition to give movement we do. Honesty of the word of the word dictionary Meaning: Conscience with , honesty on the surface the work keeping; correctness , purity . Honesty a person education through formable beautiful of virtues is one That is right on the way walk , own work live with , speaker _ and listener between of relationships strong to be for communication during , take going works during true speaking and honesty with the work to see mean is caught . From this apparently stands for the concept of " Honesty " . mutually to communicate entered persons in the middle to each other has been in relation to main place occupying them _ between confidence increase forms , mutually relationships improves , har how activity in the process honest , fair to be encourages .

"Honest sustenance search obligatory from prayers after coming is obligatory"

Imam Tabarani and Baihaqi .

" Four thing in you if you are happy : your deposit caution do , say lie non-additive , beautiful morally , you eat honest road with find if you are ."

Imam Ahmed(6)

From the above known holy Islam this is also in our religion to understanding separately accent is given The reason Islam honesty and cleanliness is religion . To him according to honest and dirty, positive or which is evaluated as negative religious , ethical and legal are norms .

Uzbek the concept of " honesty " in the language meaning (*purity , honesty , purity , transparency*) such as synonyms as in English , to the term "honesty" - " honesty " . synonym be will receive words there is They are the following own into takes : (*integrity, sincerity, truthfulness, righteousness, probity, veracity ...*)

"I would much prefer to suffer from the clean incision of an **honest** lancet than from a sweetened poison"

Mark Twain(7)

"There are people who think that **honesty** is always the best policy. This is a superstition. There are times when the appearance of it is worth six of it."

Mark Twain (8)

Above famous by Mark Twain from his works received quotes seeing we went out Floating to the concept of " Honesty ". skillfully road with tariff giving past _

From this except Mukhtar Khan Eshon Umarchoja " Kyzil". to the book don't fall feelings ” in the book this to the concept so definition giving past : “ All goodness of goodness the head is in honesty . Honesty goodness , blessing , peace such as each other with relative are feelings . We are excited tickling different from Satan's temptations saved only human pure is a human being.

Honest that you live feeling stand up happy you are human Good luck if we think , the world honesty feeling protect is coming By the way , our grandfathers he said , prayer ten from the part consists of if , his nine part honest risk is to search .

Honesty only healthy faith the owner has been in people will be Man in his life all social in relationships , marriage for in attempts to live for struggle in the process , the surrounding people with mutually in communications very necessary _ To honesty compliance did person to himself reported confidence abuse does not , others rights compliance does , undertakes task conscientiously performs ".(9)

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